

What Would Make Virtual Reality Worth Putting on Every Day for the Average
Consumer: A Scientific Method and Design Thinking Mixed-Approach to Discover,
Hypothesize, Develop, and Market in Disguise

Research and Experiment
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by
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ABSTRACT

This research set out to find what makes a *killer* Virtual Reality (VR) app. Defined as an app so essential, something so essential and instinctively worth returning to that it could anchor a headset in a non-gamer's daily life. It ended up uncovering a methodology for this emerging technology to leverage its worth using a true problem only VR is uniquely positioned to solve. In the current consumer market, VR is shaped as an escape or a portal away from physical reality into something more stimulating or spectacular than what the real world offers. Years of incentivized useage, heavy marketing, AAA games, branded experience extensions, immersive communities, attempting to help overlook the insufficient on-device compute, latency and restrictive interoperability. Decades of hardware advancement on headsets made to feel lighter, faster, useful with an expanding app ecosystem, and yet there is still is no application in the market that makes people reach specifically for the headset or stay inside it. VR headsets still sit in their box or as a decor on the shelf, underused. This research experiment applies a mixed-method approach combining the Scientific Method and Design Thinking with secondary research running through all stages, and Marketing as Disguise to conduct primary research and validate hypotheses. Findings from this research will elaborate and suggest that a considerably minimal product, solving a true problem with a VR-only solution, if paired with strategic marketing strategies and iterations based on the behavioral condition discovered and validated can lead to a killer VR app, making the headset worth putting on everyday.

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1. Introduction

The VR industry has been talking about its 'killer app' for decades (Robarts, 2024). Games already dominate the charts on headsets (LSylvia, 2025), but VR is still waiting for a must-have non-gaming app (Musa, 2025), an app so essential, so instinctively worth returning to, it justifies the headset's bulky existence in a non-gamer's life, recurringly. This research applies a mixed-method approach, running the scientific method: question, hypothesis, experiment, analysis, conclusion (Science Buddies, 2012) in parallel with design thinking: empathize, define, ideate, prototype, test, iterate (Plattner, 2010) across eight months of building, testing, and observing. As of 2026, Meta prominently features non-gaming categories such as fitness and wellness in the Quest ecosystem, but like the broader health-app market, many of these apps struggle with long-term daily retention (Popular/Trending Meta Quest Games Today, 2025). The hardware is capable now and has drastically evolved over decades, along with the growing ecosystem of virtual users mostly from games with huge cult followings (Highlights from Day 1 at GDC 2026: Hands, Agents, Performance & More, 2025), but then why has no single application still made the mass-market consumers want to put on a VR headset, and reach for it again tomorrow? My research began with that observation turned into a simple question: What makes a *killer* VR app: the app as a product, or its marketing?

Examined in two distinct parts, part one looked into the VR apps market for insights, using Design Thinking Methodology with secondary research, ideation, technical prototyping, and peer testing to discover how to make an app that makes VR feel worth putting on everyday. And part two, after running experiments with prototypes, reframes observed responses into a strategy that would make users want to not only try, but retain their attention and time in VR. Using the Scientific Method three experiences were stacked for a live user testing at an indoor public event based on user preferred features

gathered after affinity mapping, features selected from technical feasibility and research audits and results from prototype experiments in part one. This testing and event surfaced a much larger real-world problem: users placed in simple low-stimulation VR environments became bored or anxious almost immediately. That discomfort was not a design failure, it was an observation that became the data that distinguished part one and part two with a new hypothesis.

Part two reoriented the research and prototype iterations with a marketing strategy that emerged directly from an observed human behavioral condition. The strategy included a social media campaign, live events for user testings disguised as a branded experiences, global stillness movement on website and social, a VR stillness training app and championship, and exclusive portals for event champions with personalized tokens and continuity cards.

The conclusion this research moves toward loops to an iterative cycle of hypothesis observation and validation. It is an honest discovery, evidence-based analysis and strategic evaluation of making the headset worth putting on everyday. The research experiment continues to evolve in tandem with newly observed challenges after each experiment, until a hypothesis positively concludes into a killer app or similar results.

2. Research and Empathy

2.1 Mixed Reality (MR) and other Extended Reality (XR)

An early decision was to focus on full VR immersion for both technical and conceptual reasons. Mixed reality was therefore seriously considered as a foundation for the initial concepts in this research. Meta's updates around 2024–2025 significantly improved Meta Quest 3's color passthrough and mixed reality capabilities, enabling higher-fidelity blending of virtual content with the physical environment and new tools for room-scale scanning (Finnegan, 2023).

Technically, the project sought to design an application that could be evaluated as a “real-world” solution using the scientific method, which required treating platform constraints, performance limits, and third-party dependencies as first-class design constraints. To keep the experimental setup controllable, the research applied a series of technical audits to potential features and architectures. These audits led to the exclusion of several “trend” technologies: MR, real-time object detection, continuous voice/audio capture, and heavy integration of cloud-based AI for object understanding, conversational agents, or generative world-building (Meta, 2024).

On Quest 3, high-quality MR and AI-enhanced camera experiences rely on evolving APIs, resource-intensive depth and mesh processing, and in some cases battery-heavy workloads, which XR developers themselves still describe as experimental or rapidly changing (Skarredghost, 2025). Always-listening voice features and large-scale audio capture were deprioritized because they raise nontrivial privacy and compliance challenges when deployed at scale, especially if audio must be transmitted to external AI services for interpretation. From a research design perspective, tying core interaction loops to third-party AI APIs also introduces instability: providers such as OpenAI and Google Gemini frequently update models (OpenAI for Developers in 2025, 2025), deprecate preview offerings, and expand capabilities in ways that can materially change system behavior mid-study.

More broadly, early research identified three practical gaps between contemporary AI services and headset-based devices:

1. Evolving APIs and model line-ups, which complicate long-term reproducibility.
2. Significant latency when offloading spatial reasoning and multimodal analysis to cloud models, due to capture>upload>process>return cycles.

3. Limited on-device compute and memory where Meta Quest 3 ships with 8 GB of RAM, relative to the requirements of modern large language and multimodal models, which demand far larger memory budgets.

These gaps do not make AI unusable in XR, but they constrain how reliably AI-heavy features can be evaluated as part of a controlled product study in 2025-2026. The final choice of VR over MR reflects a stance on the philosophical relationship between head-mounted hardware and user experience.

Meta Quest 3 remains a relatively bulky, face-worn device even as it has become lighter and more ergonomically refined (Marshall, 2024). In MR mode, the user continues to see their real surroundings via passthrough while digital content is overlaid; it preserves complete situational awareness but keeps the physical world constantly in view even with a heavy headwear on the user's head. VR, by contrast, is designed to minimize external sensory input and replace it with a fully synthetic environment, leveraging Quest-class displays and tracking to "remove" the immediate world safely rather than overlay in it. MR's constant environmental awareness, even after putting on a heavy headwear became a technical limitation, whereas VR embraced this headset limitations as a unique property for a medium capable of removing the world. VR's total sensory occlusion is an almost radical and underused design opportunity.

2.2 VR Market Landscape and a Missing Killer App

A killer app, as established across consumer technology history, is an application so indispensable that it drives adoption of its host platform (Robarts, 2024). The term is widely used for software that is so desirable that consumers will buy hardware primarily to access it (Molina, 2025). Consumer VR, despite decades of hardware advancement and its most mature standalone headsets today, has not yet produced a widely recognized, non-gaming killer app for mainstream audiences; commentary across the

industry continues to describe VR as “still waiting” for such an application (Molina, 2025). Extensive secondary research into the Meta Quest ecosystem confirmed this perceived gap. The platform’s storefront separates “Games” and “Apps,” but these categories are deeply unequal: games dominate charts, store promotions, and most of the cultural conversation around Quest usage (LSylvia, 2025). The app category, while growing, remains fragmented across productivity tools (virtual desktops and collaborative whiteboards), fitness applications, and wellness environments that often mirror existing mobile or desktop experiences in a 3D wrapper rather than introducing fundamentally new interaction patterns (M, 2026).

VR is distinctive among consumer media in that it can substantially occlude or replace the user’s physical surroundings rather than merely overlaying content on top of them. Many current apps introduce new worlds or concepts, but few intentionally use this “world removal” property on its own as the core value; instead, they typically direct attention into alternative, fully themed environments where users are entertained or distracted. Within the non-gaming category, no single application has yet emerged as a habitual, everyday touchpoint for a broad, non-enthusiast audience, in the way that messaging, web browsing, or social feeds did for smartphones (Musa, 2025). Further analysis of top-charting non-game entries in the Quest store surfaced a consistent pattern: the most commercially successful non-gaming applications combine straightforward utility with familiar interaction paradigms from phones or desktops as a way to reduce friction and keep users engaged (LSylvia, 2025). Their primary Unique Selling Proposition (USP) tends to be functional or task-driven (for example, virtual monitors or workspace extensions) or falls into wellness and mindfulness, often through passive, guided experiences such as meditation environments, nature scenes, audio guidance, or personalized narratives that closely resemble mobile counterparts. These apps rarely require users to move their bodies in novel ways or to engage with spatial

interaction patterns unique to head-mounted displays, revealing a limited use of VR's more embodied capabilities and of the physical affordances users actually adopt when wearing a headset. Secondary research into VR User Experience (UX) guidelines and user reports around comfort and onboarding also highlighted what many users say they want from a VR app: minimal or no formal onboarding, low controller complexity or reliance, a visually striking or surreal quality that feels impossible on a phone, and an overall experience simple enough to become an easy on-and-off daily habit (Sabah et al., n.d.). When clustered and affinity-mapped, these preferences for simplicity, low friction, and originality informed the initial design criteria for prototyping and peer feedback, converging on a leading How Might We (HMW) statement: How might we make VR feel worth putting on every day?

3. Experiment One

3.1 Ideation to Prototype

The Design Thinking process began with simple brainstorming and ideation methods like Crazy 8, Worst Possible Ideas and Role Storming alongside secondary research and data point extractions. These methods reveal a creative direction and gave an insight into how different types of audiences perceive and need VR differently.

Report 1: Finding one app that fits all seemed challenging at first, but the goal with design thinking was to keep ideas flowing regardless of restrictions or assumptions. No wrong answers, just creativity. Once multiple concepts formed themselves with sketches and words, I moved ahead to mind mapping them, listing under each what functions each app might entail. Several overlapped their key functions with Daily Journaling, Audio Visual experiences, or creative playgrounds as a means of human expression or reflection.

To eliminate this repetition, further bucketing methods like bubble maps and tree maps were used to identify common features within the first eight concepts developed, ultimately compositing them to four unique concepts: Mind Palace Journal in VR, Blackout Therapy & VR Experience, Echo MR Audio Visual Experience, Artist Pond Music Maker. These were mapped out without technical or philosophical feasibility restraints. Role storming and market data analysis eliminated niche ideas like Artist Pond for commercial viability, and once technical feasibility audits were performed, concepts dependent on MR or privacy concerns were also ruled out. Narrowing down to one concept that fit user preferences and data points from affinity mapping: Blackout Therapy & VR Experience.

Report 2: Unreal Engine 5.6. with Blueprints was my main tool of creation during prototyping. Eventually, switching to Unity to compile a product that considers future SDK compatibilities and scalability with other headsets.

The experiment began very early on in this research, primarily starting with peer testing to gain feedback and simply observe what our youth feels inside the headset. Mostly aging between twenty-five to thirty, every person who entered the headset to see only darkness, got out in under five-ten seconds, with the obvious reason: “there’s nothing to do”. But there was also some magic in their tones when they didn’t seem to mind not having anything to do, even for the ten seconds.

Report 3: It seemed odd, and almost too easy, to initially prototype a fully blackout, pitch dark app. Even though all data led to a blackout VR app with a controller-free, interaction-free, hands-only tech stack and there seemed to be some unique potential to sitting in complete darkness, using a VR headset for something one can close their eyes to experience seemed unsettling. Hence, against data-point deductions, I made an additional effort to prototype two other minimal experiences and test for response variability: a dynamic audio

and visual experience, and a blackout chaotic, not therapeutic, experience.

During this feedback exchange, most peers expected gamification, claiming it as a purpose to be inside a headset device.

For interactivity without controllers, Procedural Content Generation (PCG) graphs were used to build and dynamically distribute varying 3D objects in the user's space, different in each session creating unique, non-repeating environments without hand-authoring content. This interaction layer added a sense of agency without complexity for users where the headset became a responsive instrument to stay inside, but also led the app towards feeling gamified or task-based, defeating the non-game application purpose.

3.2 Analysis to Reframing

To reframe prototypes for a live event-wide testing, with these early insights from experiment one, total three experiences were created. First, the simplest possible VR experience was the pure blackout, with calming breathing sounds - labeled *calm*. Second, a slightly more variable experience with environments procedurally changing, made responsive to the user's eye tracking and head movement, no controllers needed - labeled *explore*. And lastly, a dynamic audio based chaotic experience with sounds dispersed within a blackout experience - labeled *intense*.

4. Testing One

4.1 Event One

Mixibition 2025, a yearly event at the Mix Center in Mesa, Arizona showcases immersive experiences and digital experience from the works of ASU students and beyond (MIXibition Fall 2025 | ASU Events, 2025). This was the setting for the first large-scale user test: a two hour indoor event with high foot traffic from an audience already primed for immersive and experimental media. The event was not disclosed as a user test to any

participant, presented entirely as an experience to discover something within the space and headset.

The physical setup was deliberate in its design. A back corner of the space was enclosed in black curtains, dimly lit, entirely marketed with dark, minimal marketing: posters, take away cards, and a sandwich board, all carrying an early brand identity of a physical and virtual space to “Esc” from the frantic world outside the curtains. The space was intentionally furnished with cozy seating, ambient string lights along the floor, and a table with small tactile activities adjacent to the VR station, on the other side of the curtains, small puzzles with an open-to-all seating was available so visitors could linger without the pressure to engage with a headset, or enter a blacked out space immediately. The environment was designed to feel like a destination for comfort rather than a project demonstration; somewhere to stay, not just pass through.

Data was collected through manual duration logging in a Google Sheets tracker, informal 1:1 conversations with participants as they exited the headset, real-time behavioral observation, and an optional sticky note prompt displayed within the booth: "Where do your thoughts go?" Visitors were invited to respond on post-its and attach them to a shared board. This method of anonymous, low-pressure response was chosen specifically to collect transparent qualitative data without the bias of a formal survey or interview.

4.2 Marketing Disguise for Non-Biased Testing

The marketing at the event was designed to intrigue without explaining. The Esc branding, at this stage, offered no description of what the experience was other than what seemed obvious to the users with an only dark, minimal visuals and one-liner taglines on prints. The booth's black curtained enclosure, visible from across the corridors created a visual disruption in a space full of other colorful, active or open displays. People stopped to look before they stopped to read, and the physical space in

blackout became an attention-grabber. Several of the total 40 booth visitors mentioned they approached out of pure curiosity about what was behind the curtains. This was intentional marketing to attract people who were drawn to the aesthetic of dark cozy spaces as an escape within a crowded exhibition.

Inside the curtains, participants were not told what to expect in the headset. There was no demo video, no instruction sheet, no guided onboarding. The only framing offered was the prompt on the table: "Where do your thoughts go?", which served both as data collection and the only conceptual context given.

4.3 Observation and Empathy

Report 4: I watched how participants responded to the space itself: whether they sat down first or reached for the headset, how long they stayed after removing the headset, whether they engaged with the prompt, and what they said unprompted to the person next to them.

Qualitative data emerged more from natural expression than structured questions. Some unique responses to the sticky note prompt included "scary but love", "into our subconscious mind", "cozy", "anxiety inducing", and "I always like to rest my eyes". And the most analytically rich response of the evening received during 1:1 interactions with an exiting user: "Humans have a need to make sense of things constantly. This made you want to make sense of sounds and make a narrative, then let it go... because you can't really make sense of everything, can you."

Report 5: These were not responses to a questionnaire. They were things people said felt right after the experience ended for them, because something in blackout darkness moved them to. After considering how long people stayed in the headset total and how 1:1 testimonials shaped with people exiting the headset, my thinking reshaped towards how people respond to low

stimulations. Noticing how marketing with a cozy physical activation impacted the stays significantly.

The observation that ended Part One was ultimately not the tabulated eighty-seven minutes (one hour and twenty-seven minutes) spent inside the headset by twenty-three people. It was in the hasty exits of users who left the headset quickly, under a minute, almost universally with the same explanation: there's nothing to do. They left because the absence of a task was uncomfortable. Sitting in a dark, quiet space with no objective created an immediate low-level anxiety or restlessness that most users resolved by choosing to remove the headset to end the experience. The container had no content in darkness, nothing to see, no stimulus, direction, or something to respond to. For everyday users of any technology, the entertainment or content users reached for, within the space or headset, was not there.

Report 6: What I perceived as a feature gap at a glance, turned out to be a behavioral condition. Did the app not fail to entertain because it had succeeded in exposing that people could not sit with themselves anymore in this distraction-operated economy?

This observation, appearing repeatedly across the blackout VR sessions in a single evening and earlier in peer testings, produced a new question subsequently documented as a widespread behavioral condition.

5. Secondary Research Two

5.1 Attention Economy

This context was discovered in Testing One's live indoor session with simple controller-free VR experiences. The irony that simplicity without curation or any content creates problems for users' attention behaviour was visibly evident and became the focus that drove further Strategies.

Research across psychology and behavioral economics document a measurable erosion of human tolerance for boredom, silence, and self-directed thoughts. In a frequently cited study, participants preferred administering mild electric shocks to themselves over sitting quietly alone with their thoughts for fifteen minutes (Whitehead, 2014). The structure of the attention economy is engineered at scale to prevent stillness by constantly trying to recapture or steal undivided attention. Variable rewards, infinite scrolls, algorithmic content feeds, and notification designs are now deliberate mechanisms built to make disengagement uncomfortable, not just to increase engagement at will. The unsettling truth of dark UX and marketing, all trying to steal users' undivided attention.

5.2 Market and Competitive Research

The competitive landscape for meditative and wellness VR apps revealed a category that was crowded in quantity and thin in differentiation. Virtually every app in the space relied on the same formula: a calming natural environment, a guided voiceover, and passive consumption. The marketing for these apps followed the same logic as their design, promising relaxation as a deliverable, something the app produces for the user rather than something the user builds for themselves from within them. None of them positioned inner-stillness as a skill. None of them acknowledged the behavioral condition that makes relaxation difficult in the first place. The attention economy had produced a generation of people who could not sit quietly, and the entire wellness app category was responding by making sitting quietly easier to avoid, packaging distraction in a calmer aesthetic rather than addressing the underlying problem.

The VR digital or consumer market had no product for people who recognized they could not sit in silence with their mind and wanted to change that. The only thing missing was

a strategy that didn't tell them exactly what to search for in the dark, letting their mind discover what needs to be searched, by themselves.

6. Iteration Cycle

6.1 Compiling Version 0.1

Based on a synthesis of secondary research, peer testing, technical feasibility prototyping, and the observations from Testing One, the killer feature stack was defined around four decisions that build on each other.

The first is hands-only, controller-free interaction. The user's hands are rendered in a translucent material inside the headset, with no controllers required and no proficiency assumed. This makes the headset immediately wearable by anyone, removing the most common barrier to first-time VR use before the experience even begins. The second is dynamic breathing audio. Rather than music, narration, or a guided session, the spatial audio in the experience is a breathing sound that responds to the user's presence and physical movement. The pace of the breathwork shifts depending on the intensity of the user's motion, making the audio feel alive and personal without any instructions. The third is minimal, emergent interaction. Because the audio mirrors the user's natural movement, a sense of agency appears without the user having to learn anything or be told what to do. The environment responds to how users exist inside it, not to what they consciously input. This introduces subtle surrealism through presence alone. The fourth, and the core of this entire stack, is a total blackout VR environment. No objects, no skybox, no ambient or mesmerizing visuals, no content or task of any kind. This is the feature no other headset-based fully-immersive application in the current market offers, and also one that no medium other than VR can replicate.

6.2 Product Reframing

Together, the four features produce something that is less an application in the traditional sense and more an access to a container. The user enters the headset, the world outside disappears entirely, and what remains is the user's own body, their own breath, and a responsive darkness that neither demands nor distracts. This state is meaningfully different from simply closing one's eyes. Closing your eyes requires active muscle effort to maintain (trying to keep your eyes closed to avoid distractions), existing within the ambient sensory field of the physical room, carrying an underlying implicit awareness of the environment around. The headset blocks all of that with additional barrier. The user is physically placed inside nothingness, still present in their body, still able to feel their hands, still able to hear the shift in audio as they move, but entirely relieved of the external world or its demands. It is solitude without the strain of forcing it, **not** ask the user to relax, focus, or feel anything in particular. The app simply provides the conditions, and what the user encounters inside is entirely theirs.

7. Experiment Two

7.1 Strategy

Part One had been a study of what features could make a killer VR app and the findings from Testing One reframed the question entirely, learning that a killer VR app did not need *better* features. It needed to address a real human problem that sold itself automatically. Part Two led with a new hypothesis as its foundation: there is erosion of human tolerance for stillness in a world engineered for constant stimulation (Sharpe & Spooner, 2025). Using marketing as its method of validation, testing whether people were ready to recognize we live in a distraction optimized society.

The ideation process for marketing followed the same creative thinking as the app's concept ideation where any taglines, campaign concepts, and directions were generated freely before elimination. Dozens of directions emerged from the brainstorming: virtual

space to do nothing, anti-VR app, sit to sit challenge, escape from escape, 1:1 with your mind, what is in your mind, choose your path between silence or chaos, etc. The recurring tension being selecting a direction that named the discomfort most people felt but had not articulated.

Three distinct strategies were developed from these directions, each with unique positions. The first, Meditate Different, framed the app as a self-growth experience where users could find peace in silence or intensity, calming agitation or stirring extreme calm. The second, Sit With Your Mind, led with the problem directly: eliminate the dopamine distractions, sit with yourself, feel your feelings, and escape your limits. This was the blackout app marketed as the first app to do nothing. The third, Sensory Slider, positioned the app as an anti-VR or anti-escape product, switching out feelings through scalable virtual room concepts. All three were designed to brand the same underlying app. The distinction between them was not what the product did but what problem it named and who it spoke to.

Sit With Your Mind was selected as the only direction that did not hedge, naming the behavioral problem without softening it, positioned the product as a response rather than a remedy, and left room for both the silence and chaos experiences to coexist under one honest premise.

7.2 Marketing Campaign

The problem this campaign was built around was stated plainly: people avoid their feelings, easily distracting themselves with devices and disposable dopamine. The opportunity that followed was equally plain: offering anti-dopamine in a dopamine economy. And the product proposition that emerged from both was: escape the demand to be entertained constantly. Your hands, your breath, your mind.

Phase one was a social media campaign built on an anti-post strategy. Rather than producing content designed to compete for attention in an algorithmic feed, the posts were designed to disrupt it. Blackout video reels with only breathing audio, no color, no movement, no hook in the conventional sense. Captions were written as quiet provocations: *“the loudest thing you will hear today is nothing”*, *“your mind awaits”*, *“nothing to solve, only yourself to meet”*. Posted three to seven times a week across Instagram, the campaign produced over twenty seven thousand total organic views to an account that started from zero, without paid promotion. The strategy was to attract an early audience that self-selected into the aesthetic of nothingness before the product was ever explained to them.

Phase two was physical activation. The same app and the same problem brought into a public space through portable stillness stations at high traffic events, re-framing to a sitting challenge: sit with your mind in VR for five minutes (or as long as you can), beat the global high score. A QR code at the booth led to the website where scores were posted, a join list was available, and the first glimpse of the public stillness movement was visible. The website positioned the experience not as an app launch but as the beginning of a global championship, a public invitation to find out how long you could last with nothing but your own presence. Plans for the activation extended beyond events to fast-paced, high-stress locations: gyms, airports, co-working spaces, anywhere people arrive already overwhelmed and leave with less capacity for stillness than when they entered.

Phase three was the conversion of participants into a community. Physical event champions received exclusive early-access portals to the app and continuity cards as tangible proof of their practice. This along with grounding tokens were designed as artifacts of an experience represented closer to a sobriety chip than branded merchandise or promotional items. A wearable evidence that the practice was real,

portable, and belonged to the person carrying it. The goal of this phase was not to build a user base in the conventional sense. It was to find a cult, a small, self-selected group of people who had found the aesthetic of nothingness before it had a name, who self-recognized the problem the campaign was describing, and wanted to be part of the first community organized around training the mind's capacity to be still. The structure of this three-phase campaign was designed to test the new hypothesis observed from peer testing to Testing One and in continued research for validation.

8. Testing Two

8.1 Event Metrics

Change the World 2026 is an ASU innovation event held outdoors at a stadium venue in Tempe, Arizona, drawing an audience oriented toward world-changing ideas, entrepreneurship, and emerging technology (Change the World | ASU Events, 2026). The event ran outdoors for two hours and thirty minutes, with consistent foot traffic throughout. This was the setting for the second large-scale user test, and like the first, it was not disclosed as research to any participant. The entire setup was presented as an experience and a sitting challenge.

The physical installation this time was stripped back and exposed. Two rocking chairs on a rubber foam mat, outlined with string lights on the ground, sat in the open air of the outdoor plaza. Two Meta Quest 3 headsets. An A-frame sign reading "NOTHING TO SEE. SERIOUSLY", a sign-in table beside it with a laptop for duration logging, a small wooden box of tokens, and printed cards. Users had the choice to put on noise cancelling headphones, yet only one seemed to want to isolate completely from the outside world. This time there were also no curtains, no enclosure. The full space was visible from a distance across the event floor, which meant every person who walked past could see someone sitting completely still in a VR headset, outdoors, surrounded by the noise and

activity of a live event including a concert playing in the background from a nearby stage. That visibility became its own form of marketing.

Data was collected through real-time duration logging in a Google Sheets tracker, behavioral observation of how participants approached and exited the experience, and informal 1:1 conversations with participants after they removed the headset. A total of thirteen participants out of the thirty two space visitors sat for a five minute sitting challenge tabulating to eighty-eight minutes (one hour twenty-eight minutes) spent inside a headset, again by choice, in a fully blackout experience. This outdoor setting introduced so many variables that the indoor event had not. The noise of the stadium, a concert running in the background, heavy chatter not just footfall, created a significantly higher barrier to stillness for most of the evening. And yet people sat, five whole minutes and longer.

8.2 Marketing Validation from Non-Biased Testing

The brand presented at this event had a name for the first time: **Mynded**, Stillness Training in VR. The rebrand from Esc to Mynded reflected the shift in framing that had happened between the two events where the first event tested whether people would even want to sit in a headset experience themed on darkness and the second, tested whether people would accept being still without anything to see or do. Testing whether a brand built entirely around nothingness could hold its own sternly, in a loud, fast, visually competitive outdoor environment.

The sandwich board at the entrance of the booth, also the first thing visible from a distance, performed exactly as the blackout social content had on Instagram: the refusal to compete for attention became the attention-getter. Several participants approached specifically because the sign confused or intrigued them. The challenge framing was explicit from the start in this event, participants were told to sit in VR for five minutes

(or longer if wanted), their time would be tracked, and the person with the longest duration would be the event champion, receiving exclusive early access to the app. A QR code within posters and banners linked to the website, where a Lifetime Global Champions leaderboard was displayed alongside a "Join the Movement" call to action to the social movement.

Champions and participants received physical tokens at the start of their session: black string of beads, chosen for their tactile weight and simplicity, as a grounding object to feel or fidget with when sitting in the headset. Event champions, exactly when they reached their five-minute completion mark, received a printed card reading "I CAN SIT WITH MY FEELINGS," alongside an exclusive link to a private event portal accessible only to people who had participated in person. The portal contained early information to the stillness movement, engaging stillness activities and approaches, winner insights and an invitation to become part of the ongoing development community. Both, the takeaway beads and artifacts were designed to make the practice feel like something that belonged to the person who had done it. Personal and confidential to only them.

9. Analysis

9.1 Zero to One results

None of the primary metrics in this research would exist without an early decision to experiment, test and market before the product was ready. There was no finished app, no launched brand, no social following, and no established user base when the first public event took place. There was a prototype, a problem observed through peer testing, and a booth at an immersive arts event, producing twenty three voluntary sessions in a blackout VR experience from forty strangers within two hours. Had the research waited for the app to be polished, the campaign to be finalized, or the brand to be fully

developed, none of the behavioral data appearing and shaping subsequent hypothesis would exist, neither would its next iteration or strategy.

Marketing was part of this process from the beginning, not because the product needed promotion, but because the research needed disguise. Asking people whether they wanted to sit in a dark VR headset and do nothing would have produced one kind of data; watching whether they chose to, observing for how long and testing to elongate that, produced something more honest. The decision to embed primary research inside a live marketing experiment meant that every metric gathered across both events and the social campaign was behavioral, not reported. No participant knew they were being studied and every data point was earned by the product earning attention first.

The zero-to-one arc of this research runs from a handwritten observation turned HMW statement in September 2025 to a launched app with a named brand, a private early-access community, a global stillness movement with over twenty-seven thousand organic content views by April 2026.

9.2 Comparing and Evaluating Testing One and Two

The most immediately visible difference between the two events is the conversion rate: 57.5% at Event 1 and 40.6% at Event Two. The indoor setting at Mixibition, the enclosed black curtain booth, and the immersive arts audience created conditions closer to the product's natural context. The outdoor setting at Change the World, with no enclosure, a stadium concert playing in the background, and an innovation-focused crowd moving quickly between booths, raised the bar for voluntary engagement. That 40.6% of visitors still chose to sit in a VR headset, knowing well there will be nothing to see inside, close themselves off from a loud outdoor event for a five minute challenge to just sit.

The numbers for Event Two seem lower, but behind that metric are *tougher* conditions like a concert in the background, heavy consistent footfall, open area with each user

visible in daylight and a challenge rather than just a choice to sit for a total of five minutes at least. This challenge framing, is what led to only one user stepping out before the five minute ended, logged as a fail only because the participant's phone rang mid-session. This challenge framing introduced at Event Two, sit as long as you can, beat the score, placed every session inside a competitive context that made an immediate exit feel like a forfeit rather than a choice. The reframe from experience to training changed the terms of participation.

Maximum duration moved from fifteen minutes at Event One to sixteen minutes at Event Two, in meaningfully different environments. But it's important to note that the participant who reached sixteen minutes was the final user of the evening, sitting outdoors after the concert had ended and most of the event crowd had left. Their own words made this even more evident: "the quiet that arrived at the end made it easy to stay". The comparison between the two locations surfaces what conditions matter to progressively achieve stillness, a key data point for the next phases. Enclosure helped at Event One, silence helped at Event One, and a challenge framing raised the bar across sessions. The conditions that support stillness are not elaborate or complicated, they're just rare in an environment that supports distractions better.

Report 7: An additional observation from Event Two worth noting (absent in Event One) is that the fifth participant sat for a tracked time extension of three minutes outside the headset after removing it, and also stayed to chat for a while longer than any other participant as well. Another user who completed their session brought two referral participants to the booth. One of the sitters also offered to be involved in the campaign and the brand "Mynded", sitting a total of 11 minutes amidst the high chaos of the event (second highest).

These behaviors were not prompted. They suggest that the experience produced something people wanted to process and share, which is a different outcome from the typical event demo interaction.

9.3 Result Discussion

Across eight months of research, two public events, a social campaign, and a launched product, the data consistently pointed in the same direction: people who were given the conditions for stillness, without being asked whether they wanted it, chose it in numbers that a conventional product launch process would not have predicted or even looked for. The 57.5% and 40.6% VR conversion rates at two very different public events reflect voluntary engagement with an unknown product in environments where dozens of competing experiences were available. Not only that, but it also marks the attention spans of audiences with 15 and 16 minute maximum sessions, reflecting first-time users making an unsolicited decision to remain inside a dark, silent, headset longer than most people sit quietly in any medium or environment. Such undivided attention, for that duration, is a rare find in the fast-paced content economy. Globally, this was validated by the 27K+ organic views on blackout social content with an audience that recognized something useful in a black screen with breathing audio before the product behind it had a name.

The research did not set out to prove that people wanted stillness. It set out to build a feature stack for a killer VR app that can make the headset worth putting on and observed what the features revealed by human behavior and user decisions.

10. Conclusion to Iteration Loop

10.1 Data Study

None of the numbers were targets, merely observations that the research did not set out to prove. Within two events and a total of seventy-two booth visitors, thirty-six chose to enter a VR headset voluntarily, knowing there was nothing to see inside. Combining a total of two hours and fifty-five minutes of voluntary stillness accumulated by strangers at an indoor showcase and an outdoor innovation festival, plus a social campaign that reached over twenty-seven thousand organic views from zero views or follower only by posting black screens with breathing audio. Maximum session duration of fifteen minutes at the first event and sixteen at the second were also achieved by first-time users in a very public settings with competing stimulation nearby. Sitting quietly in darkness for fifteen or sixteen minutes, voluntarily, at a crowded setting, is not a default behavior in 2025 or 2026.

In a category like VR defined by complexity, novelty, and surreal spectacles, a product that works by removing all three and replacing it with pitch blackout is a meaningful result. But this paper does not claim that Mynded is the killer VR app the industry has been waiting for since the evidence is too early and the scale too small to make that claim with confidence.

What the evidence does support is narrower and more durable: a true behavioral problem, observed through live testing and validated through a disguised marketing campaign, can be addressed by a product so minimal it has almost no content, and that users will choose it voluntarily in conditions where more stimulating alternatives are available. In this case, the headset is used as a means to remove the world and create the absence of content, leaving users with their own presence.

10.2 What Makes a Killer VR App?

The question that opened this study was whether a killer VR app is made by the product or its marketing. After eight months of prototyping, two public events, a social campaign,

and a launched product, the honest answer is that the question was the wrong one. It assumed the killer app was something to be built toward. What the research showed is that it is something to be discovered, and that discovery requires a specific method, not a better feature set.

That method emerged from running the scientific method and design thinking simultaneously rather than sequentially. Not just as a theoretical framework, but as a practical necessity where the scientific method alone would have ended the research the first time a hypothesis was falsified when users in a minimal VR environment left quickly and reported nothing to do, and Design thinking alone would have responded to that discomfort by adding content. Running both together produced a third move: treating the discomfort as the finding, empathizing, and asking what it revealed about the person rather than about the product.

It revealed that people cannot sit with themselves. Not comfortably. Not even for five minutes. It is the documented behavioral output of an economy engineered to make stillness feel like a waste of time. An observation that didn't come from a literature review, but from live watching people take off a VR headset, and say the same thing on the way out.

VR removes the world not as a metaphor, but by physically occluding the user's environment, cutting off the ambient visual field that anchors them to their to-do list and their phone, placing them inside whatever the developer chose to put there. That property of **removing** the world has been used, almost universally, to replace the world with something more stimulating. Games, social spaces, cinematic experiences, fitness environments. The entire commercial logic of VR has been: if we remove the world, fill the space with something better. This research proposes the inverse where removal is the product. What the user finds in the space when nothing is placed there is not emptiness, but themselves.

10.3 Mixed-Method Approach

The stillness problem and the VR occlusion property are a problem-platform intersection, not just two separate insights that *happened to converge*. A specific condition where a real human behavioral need meets the one medium structurally capable of addressing it. Every killer app in the history of consumer technology has lived at exactly this intersection. The telephone and the problem of distance; the smartphone and the problem of presence; the search engine and the problem of information access; none of those were designed toward that intersection, just a discovery of it through use, through watching what people actually did with the technology once it was available. This research and experiment proposes that an intersection as such can be found deliberately as well, through the parallel application of scientific inquiry and human-centered design, with marketing deployed not as promotion but as a behavioral instrument for testing cultural resonance before the product is finished.

In theory, this methodology also seems open to any emerging platform that has not yet found its essential application, by definition a platform whose unique property has not yet been matched to the human condition it is most capable of addressing. The process for finding that match, the parallel cycle of scientific testing and empathetic interpretation, with marketing as validation and test, may be the contribution that outlasts this particular product (Mynded) and this particular problem (Stillness) but that hypothesis requires testing on other platforms, with other problems, by other researchers. This paper is one instance on one platform taking one behavioral condition to build one product. While it is enough to propose the method, it is not enough to prove it generalizes across many emerging products yet.

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APPENDIX

Figure 1: Scientific Method

Figure 2: Design Thinking Methodology

Figure 3: Mixed-Method Cycle

Table 1: Mixed-Method Evaluation

Image 1: Secondary Research (Data Points, Clusters, How Might We Statement (HMW))

Image 2: Brainstorming (Crazy 8, Role Storming, Worst Possible Idea)

Image 3: Ideation (Mind Map, Bubble Map, Tree Map)

Table 2: Feature Feasibility Experiment and Conclusion

Image 4: Prototypes (Development)

Image 5: Prototypes (Demos)

Figure 4: Event one Metric Chart

Image 6: Event one

Image 7: Stacked Killer App

Figure 5: Event two Metric Chart

Image 8: Event two

Image 9: Marketing and Branding

Image 10: Campaign

Image 11: Event Portal

Table 3: Comparison Metric for Event one and two

Figure 6: Instagram Campaign Analytics: Views & Followers @mynded_vr (January-May 2026)

Figure 1: Scientific Method

Figure 2: Design Thinking Methodology

Figure 3: Mixed-Method Cycle

Table 1: Mix-Method Evaluation

Evaluation Metrics	Design Thinking Traits	Scientific Method Traits
Purpose	Creation	Discovery
Problem types	Complex socio-technical questions	Specific, contained questions
Problem Qualities	Invite the intangible	Seek the tangible
Problem Framing	Empathize with human needs	Identify problem phenomena
Attitude	Seek new possibilities	Seek probable answers
Collaborative Approach	Integrative	Specialized
Experimental Method	Prototype quick solutions to learn	Run controlled tests to learn
Goal	Continuous improvement	Finding 'truth'

Image 1: Secondary Research (Data Points, Clusters, How Might We Statement (HMW))

Image 2: Brainstorming (Crazy 8, Role Storming, Worst Possible Idea)

Worst Possible Ideas

- too expensive
- too loud
- too complex
- too intense
- too traumatic
- too dark
- triggering
- similar to social media
- wrongly addictive
- obsessive
- used more than 3 times a day
- nothing too actually do in the app
- too niche
- comes across as only for a certain type of people
- ends up not being used after a couple uses
- shelved

Learning Outcomes:

- UX matters
- Ethics matters
- Objective matters

Role Storming Crazy 8

HMW make VR feel worth putting on every day for:

VR Developers:
Innovative, sparks idea creation. Collaborative, helps you meet other developers.

Humans part of the VR industry:
Well designed, innovative, sells well, raises industry value. raise the value of their app or gives them an incentive to re-use.

Humans who are parents:
Relaxing and relieving. Break from all the noise and responsibilities. Not too much effort. Not distracting and can be used when kids are in the house.

Little Humans:
Exciting, educational with fun means and short, iterative, and evolving to keep attention. Explorative.

Humans now retired from work:
Entertaining enough to consume time without feeling like effort. Fun, but not too excessive with the exercise or movement.

Humans working in tech:
Innovative, Creative, Sells in the market, easy to use, quality, slightly addictive.

Humans working in white collar industries:
Well developed and quality. Trends or sells in the market, slightly addictive. Smartly made. Clear objective.

Humans working in blue collar industries:
Relaxing and less manual effort. Explorative with a little whimsy.

Humans with a sense of art &/or music:
Innovative, sparks creativity. Collaborative, helps you find other artists. Helps you sell your art.

One:

- Switch between environments and realities with a hand dial watch. Go from serene to intense, personalize settings for a preferred reality.

Two:

- Build music or art from shapes.
- Mold music by molding shapes.
- Store music/art in shapes or objects.
- Collect or store what you make.
- Audio to visual connection.

Three:

- Blackout
- Listen, feel for objects that are around you virtually.
- Dark room.

Four:

- Music in the air.
- Floating, interactive, touch for sound.
- Sit, stand, dance, stroll, any movement created sound.
- Just can't see anything.
- Spotlight or minor glows.

Five:

- Floating in outer space.
- Expanded human perspective as they stay in darkness and eventually discover with a silver of light they're floating in space towards the end.

Six:

- Ethical of real world environment in MR
- Disrupt reality

Seven:

- Artist and music pond.
- Every ripple causes a new music to overlap
- Stillness will keep the music going. Each movement will overlap to a new sound.
- Once gone it doesn't come back.

Eight:

- Mind Palace
- Thought storing bubbles floating around a space.
- Record audio and store.
- Virtual mind storage with different rooms/areas to compartmentalize thoughts (garden, library, but inspired versions).
- Color attached to bubbles.

Ideas after crazy 8 - move to mind map

- What if you could move around to listen to whispers of other people thoughts?

Table 2: Feature Feasibility Experiment and Conclusion

Feature	Technical specs	Technical blockers	Conclusion
AI and XR <i>AI-driven interaction</i>	Plugin setup via OpenAI and Gemini API integration with XR SDK; object detection, conversational AI, generative world-building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • API instability (frequent OpenAI and Gemini changes) • Spatial reasoning latency (capture, cloud processing, return) • On-device compute insufficient (Quest 3 RAM 8GB vs. LLM requirements) 	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">Not interoperable</div> Ruled out. No viable path to stable on-device or cloud-synced AI in VR as of Oct 2025.
PCG <i>Procedurally generated content</i>	Randomised distribution of manually authored objects; dynamic inputs and outputs per session via PCG graphs in Unreal Engine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited asset database constrains variety • Outputs feel gamified and task-based, contradicting minimal design intent 	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">Non-recurring</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">Narrative reliant</div> Rejected. Introduced gamification and required authored content to sustain use.
Dynamic audio <i>Spatially responsive sound</i>	Standard spatial audio SDK; breathing audio responsive to head movement and intensity via Blueprint scripting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No technical blockers at standard implementation level 	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">Narrative reliant</div> Effective only with a defined emotional or content frame to give the audio meaning on return.
Surreal visuals <i>Reality-bending environments</i>	Unreal Engine 5 rendering pipeline; procedural or hand-authored environments with dynamic lighting and physics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No technical blockers at standard implementation level 	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">Narrative reliant</div> Requires strong content direction to retain users beyond novelty of first session.
Mixed reality <i>MR passthrough overlay</i>	Meta Quest 3 Hyperspace passthrough; MR hand tracking; AI object detection SDK (Unity only); AR-style overlay blending with physical environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • API instability (OpenAI and Gemini interoperability unresolved, Oct 2025) • Spatial reasoning latency too high for real-time MR response • On-device compute insufficient for local LLM execution • Headset bulk unjustified without full sensory occlusion • Physical environment remains visible, undermining stillness container 	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">Not interoperable</div> Ruled out. Technical and philosophical blockers aligned. MR cannot remove the world.

Image 4: Prototypes (Development)

Image 5: Prototypes (Demos)

Figure 4: Event one Metric Chart

Session duration data from 23 VR users sorted by ascending time. Conversion rate represents users who entered VR out of total booth visitors. All data collected during live activation event.

Image 6: Event one

Image 7: Stacked Killer App

Figure 5: Event two Metric Chart

<i>total visitors</i> 32	<i>users in VR</i> 13	<i>conversion rate</i> 40.6%	<i>total VR time</i> 88 min
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■ visitors not in VR ■ users in VR

Visitor breakdown

Session durations (minutes) - 13 sessions

Session duration data from 13 VR users sorted by ascending time. Conversion rate represents users who entered VR out of total booth visitors. All data collected during live activation event.

Image 8: Event two

Image 9: Marketing and Branding

Two clear ice cubes with the 'ESC' logo are shown at the top left. To their right is a 'Quiet Zone' sign with a crossed-out phone icon and the text 'Try to leave your voices and limit screen use in this area please. Silence your phones.' Below the ice cubes is a paragraph: 'Sensory pause in a frantic world. Sit, stand, chill in a virtual & physical space to meet your mind and to face the inevitable, deep thoughts. Hosted by Vodka B.' The bottom of the graphic features several logos and QR codes: 'Floor 3, Game Lounge Mixibition Fall 2025' with 'ASU MIX Center' logos; 'Floor 3, Game Lounge Mixibition Fall 2025' with 'ASU MIX Center' logos; 'ASU' logos; 'CHANGE THE WORLD' logo; 'MENTAL ENDURANCE & BREATHING CHALLENGE' with a QR code; 'MYNDED TRAINED STILLNESS IN VR' with a QR code; and 'March 18, 5pm - 8pm Mountain America Stadium 500 E Veterans Way, Tempe' with a QR code.

Floor 3, Game Lounge
Mixibition Fall 2025

ASU
MIX Center

Floor 3, Game Lounge
Mixibition Fall 2025

ASU
MIX Center

ASU

CHANGE THE WORLD

Nothing to see,
seriously.

I can sit with my feelings

IN A WORLD OPTIMIZED FOR DISTRACTIONS
PROVE YOU CAN STILL SIT WITH YOURSELF

MENTAL ENDURANCE & BREATHING CHALLENGE

MYNDED TRAINED STILLNESS IN VR

March 18, 5pm - 8pm
Mountain America Stadium
500 E Veterans Way, Tempe

Image 10: Campaign

Image 11: Event Portal

Table 3: Comparison Metric for Event one and two

Metric	Event 1, Mesa, Dec 2025	Event 2, Tempe, Mar 2026
Setting	Indoor (enclosed booth)	Outdoor (open sky plaza)
Brand	Esc (sensory experience)	Mynded (stillness challenge)
Event Duration	2 hrs	2.5 hrs
Total Visitors	40	32
Users in VR	23	13
VR Conversion Rate	57.5%	40.6%
Longest Duration	15 mins	16 mins
Shortest Duration	>30 secs	2.2 minutes
Total VR Time	87 mins (1 hr 27 mins)	88.07 mins (1 hr 28 mins)

Figure 6: Instagram Campaign Analytics: Views & Followers @mynded_vr (January-May 2026)

total views (90 days) 27,813	accounts reached 16,772	followers 19	non-follower views 99.4%
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Post view data points extracted from top-content analytics screenshots. Follower line uses confirmed start (0) and current count (19) with estimated intermediate values. All content is organic Reels; 99.4% of views from non-followers.